

E-SUPPLEMENT

Lung and chest wall mechanics during positive end-expiratory pressure inflation. I.

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Fig. 1. Breath-by-breath build-up of a new PEEP/EELV equilibrium in model. Note, that transpulmonary pressure at end-inspiration of a tidal volume of 500 ml (in red square) is equal to transpulmonary pressure at end-expiration at a PEEP of 10 cmH₂O and a ΔEELV of 500 ml, i.e. an increase in EELV of 500 ml above FRC (in red square).

Fig. 2.

Upper panel: Original registration (L. Chen of Brochard group, Toronto) of airway, and esophageal pressure at 5 and 15 cmH₂O of PEEP of patient in Chen et al. *Am J Resp Crit Care Med* 2020;201(2):178-87 (2).

Lower panel: whole lines inserted to eliminate cardiac pressure variations to enhance analysis. These curves are used in figure 14 of main paper.

Calculation of the lung P/V curve

The calculation of a lung P/V curve during a PEEP trial can be performed using end-expiratory and end-inspiratory airway pressure and measurements of Δ EELV by the cumulative expiratory tidal volume method (3), i.e. without using esophageal pressure data. Besides being simpler, this improves precision of measurements, as precision of esophageal pressure measurements is hampered by their dependency on the calibration procedure, the Baydur maneuver, as esophageal pressure is not representative of mean pleural pressure (1). The Baydur maneuver is regarded as acceptable if the Δ PES during the maneuver is within a range of 0.8 – 1.2 of the Δ PAW caused by the compression of the thorax (4), which means that Δ PES precision is very low.

Determining Δ EELV

For the highest precision of Δ EELV measurement, Δ EELV should be determined directly and not indirectly as the difference of EELV measurements by nitrogen washin/washout (N_2 Wi/Wo) between two PEEP levels. The N_2 Wi/Wo method (5) has typically a variability in measurements of $\pm 10\%$. In a case with an EELV of 1800 ml at the low PEEP, and 2100 ml at the high PEEP level, i.e. a Δ EELV of 300 ml, the EELV at the low PEEP can be between 1620 and 1980 ml and EELV at the high PEEP level can be between 1890 and 2310 ml. Consequently, Δ EELV can be between 690 ml and -90 ml, which is an unacceptable span.

In contrast, determination of Δ EELV by the cumulative expiratory tidal volume difference method (3) is very precise as the inspiratory tidal volume varies less than 1% (see e-supplement of (6)) and can be regarded as constant during a PEEP step maneuver. Thus, in fact the method determines Δ EELV *directly* as the cumulative difference in only expiratory tidal volume. We have made repeated PEEP steps in ARDS patients and shown that in its revised version the precision of Δ EELV measurement is $\pm 3\%$ (6), which in the above described case would mean that a Δ EELV of 300 ml would be between 291 and 309 ml. Our method for direct measurement of Δ EELV is not just an estimation, it is a very precise measurement method.

Fig. 3. Breath-by-breath $\Delta EELV$ after increasing PEEP. The red bars indicate the detained expiratory volume. The red digits are the breath $\Delta EELV$. The black digits above volume curve indicates the expiratory volume during each breath after increasing PEEP. During the first expiration after increasing PEEP, $\Delta EELV$ increases with a full expiratory volume, which is detained when the expiratory valve of the ventilator closes at the selected PEEP level, as PEEP is equal to end-inspiratory pause pressure at baseline ventilation.

Basic one-step PEEP procedure

PEEP is increased from baseline clinical level 6-10 cmH₂O and then back again. $\Delta EELV$ up and down is determined and the procedure is finalized by setting the tidal volume to the mean of $\Delta EELV$ up and down.

Fig. 4. Basic PEEP step procedure. Roman digits are referring to the three different parts of the measurement procedure. The arabic digits are identifying end-inspiratory and end-expiratory P/V points where transpulmonary pressure can be determined. Italics indicate where transpulmonary pressure only is estimated.

Fig. 5. P/V diagram of basic procedure. Red arrows: tidal airway P/V curves. Blue arrows: tidal transpulmonary P/V curves. Dashed blue line: estimated curve based on the assumption that chest wall elastance is almost constant when increasing PEEP.

Extended two-step PEEP procedure

PEEP is increased in two steps from baseline level and then lowered again from the highest PEEP level to the first PEEP level above baseline. $\Delta EELV$ up and down for the highest PEEP step are determined and the tidal volume is set equal to mean $\Delta EELV_2$. Then PEEP is lowered to baseline PEEP level and $\Delta EELV$ up and down for the first PEEP step is determined and the procedure finalized by setting the tidal volume equal to mean $\Delta EELV_1$.

Fig. 6. Basic PEEP step procedure. Roman digits are referring to the three different parts of the measurement procedure. The arabic digits are identifying end-inspiratory and end-expiratory P/V points where transpulmonary pressure can be determined. Italics indicate where transpulmonary pressure only is estimated.

Fig. 7. P/V diagram of extended procedure basic procedure. Red arrows: tidal airway P/V curves. Blue arrows: tidal transpulmonary P/V curves. Dashed blue line: estimated curve based on the assumption that chest wall elastance is almost constant when increasing PEEP.

Fig. 8. A best fit lung P/V curve is determined from the seven P/V points marked in figure 6. The dashed blue line indicate that the end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure/volume point at the highest PEEP level is estimated, rather than determined. Any tidal lung P/V curve will move up and down this best fit lung P/V curve. Starting the measurement procedure at a clinical baseline PEEP of ≈ 8 cmH₂O, and then increasing PEEP to ≈ 14 and further to ≈ 20 cmH₂O, makes it possible to identify the PEEP level where the transpulmonary driving pressure is lowest (least injurious) for any chosen tidal volume (7). The whole procedure is less than 10 minutes long.

Calibration of esophageal balloon positioning and filling

The implication of the coinciding end-expiratory airway, end-expiratory transpulmonary and tidal inspiratory P/V curves are, that when the tidal volume is equal to $\Delta EELV$, the tidal pleural pressure variations are equal to the difference between the end-inspiratory airway pressure from the low PEEP and the end-expiratory airway pressure of the high PEEP (Fig. 9). For somebody who wants to use esophageal pressure, the correct filling of the balloon will be achieved when the tidal esophageal pressure changes are equal to $PAW_{Ei_{LOPEEP}} - PAW_{EE_{HIPEEP}}$, as this is a **true** mean pleural tidal pressure swing.

Fig.9. Tidal P/V curves: airway: red arrows, lung (transpulmonary): blue arrows, chest wall (pleura): green arrows. Dashed green line: end-expiratory chest wall P/V curve ($\Delta P_{PLEE}/\Delta EELV$).

PEEP has been increased so $\Delta EELV$ has increased to a level equal to the tidal volume at baseline PEEP (500 ml), as $\Delta EELV$ is determined by the size of the PEEP step (10 cmH₂O) and lung elastance (20 cmH₂O/L). End-expiratory transpulmonary pressure increase, calculated as $\Delta EELV \times EL$, is 10 cmH₂O, and this means that end-expiratory transpulmonary pressure at the high PEEP level is equal to the end-inspiratory transpulmonary pressure of the tidal volume at baseline PEEP, which means that the transpulmonary driving pressure of a tidal volume equal to $\Delta EELV$, is equal to $\Delta PEEP$. **Consequently, transpulmonary pressure at a certain lung volume level is independent of mode of inflation: tidal or PEEP inflation and the tidal pleural pressure changes are equal to $PAW_{Ei_{LOPEEP}} - PAW_{EE_{HIPEEP}}$.**

References

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